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Modified Inverse Weibull Distribution: Using Python Approach to Evaluate Customer Transaction Data

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Abstract

Objectives: To investigate the Modified Inverse Weibull Distribution (MIWD) to determine its effectiveness in modelling real customer transaction data, which is often skewed and exhibits heavy-tailed characteristics. **Methods:** Parameters of the model were estimated using the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) technique. The model's performance was evaluated using goodness-of-fit measures, such as the log-likelihood (ℓ), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), and Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) statistic. The probability density function (PDF), cumulative distribution function (CDF), hazard function, and survival function were derived analytically and visualized with Python to assess model behavior and data alignment. **Findings:** The MIWD demonstrated a better fit for the customer transaction data than its sub-models and other competing distributions. The estimated probability density function (PDF), cumulative distribution function (CDF), hazard, and survival functions highlighted the model's adaptability in representing both skewness and heavy-tailed characteristics in actual transaction data. **Novelty:** The main contribution of this study is the empirical validation of the four-parameter MIWD using actual customer transaction data, demonstrating its superiority over established sub-models based on various quantitative criteria. The findings provide compelling evidence that the MIWD is a robust and adaptable alternative for modelling skewed, heavy-tailed transaction and lifetime data, with practical applications in customer behavior analysis, reliability engineering, and risk modelling.

Keywords: Modified Inverse Weibull Distribution; Maximum Likelihood Estimation; Customer transaction data; Parameters; Rayleigh distribution

1 Introduction

The Weibull distribution is widely recognized as a key statistical model for examining the lifespan, durability, and fatigue characteristics of engineering materials and systems. Its use extends across various fields, such as automotive engineering, electronics, aerospace systems, materials science, and reliability analysis. Due to its straightforward mathematical nature and ease of interpretation, the Weibull model has become a

standard tool for analyzing lifetime data, leading to the development of numerous specialized Weibull-based methods in recent years⁽¹⁾. With the progress in modern computational technologies, these methods have become more accessible to professionals in engineering and applied statistics. Despite its extensive application, the traditional Weibull distribution has significant limitations when dealing with complex real-world datasets. Its performance is heavily influenced by the shape and scale parameters, which impose restrictive assumptions on the probability density and hazard functions⁽²⁾. Consequently, the Weibull distribution often struggles to accurately represent datasets with pronounced skewness, heavy tails, or nonmonotonic hazard rates. While the Weibull model has shown high precision in certain applications such as modeling drying kinetics where standardized Weibull models closely matched predicted and experimental moisture values⁽³⁾ its flexibility is often inadequate for many modern applications involving diverse and highly variable data. To address these limitations, a substantial body of research has proposed extensions and generalizations of the Weibull distribution. Bayesian methods using Gibbs sampling and progressive Type-II censored data have been developed to enhance parameter estimation and interval inference⁽⁴⁾. However, these approaches mainly improve inferential procedures without fundamentally addressing the limited structural flexibility of the original Weibull model. Other generalizations, like the Harris extended Weibull distribution, have been introduced for reliability modeling and acceptance sampling plans⁽⁵⁾, yet these models often maintain restrictive hazard assumptions that limit their applicability to complex datasets. Further advancements include four-parameter lifetime models based on mixtures of exponentiated Weibull distributions⁽⁶⁾ and the Topp–Leone Weibull distribution (TLWD)⁽⁷⁾, which enhance flexibility and goodness of fit based on likelihood-based criteria. Nonetheless, many of these models are validated using limited or highly specific datasets, and their performance may decline when applied to data characterized by extreme skewness or heavy tails. Other studies focus on E-Bayesian estimation under different prior assumptions⁽⁸⁾, emphasizing estimator properties rather than addressing inherent model inadequacies. Although bimodal Weibull distributions have been proposed to handle data from mixed populations, they often introduce additional complexity and challenges in interpretation. Overall, existing Weibull and Weibull-type models either impose restrictive distributional assumptions, lack sufficient flexibility to capture heavy-tailed and highly skewed data, or concentrate primarily on estimation techniques rather than model structure. These limitations become particularly apparent when analyzing customer transaction data, which often exhibit long-tailed distributions, high variability, and complex hazard rate behavior over time. Such characteristics necessitate more adaptable lifetime models capable of capturing diverse distributional shapes within a unified framework.

Driven by these challenges, the primary aim of this research is to present and evaluate a new lifetime model called the Modified Inverse Weibull Distribution (MIWD), which was initially proposed to offer greater flexibility than the traditional inverse Weibull family⁽⁹⁾. The MIWD includes an extra parameter that greatly enhances the adaptability of the probability density and hazard functions, allowing the model to more effectively capture skewness, heavy tails, and diverse hazard rate structures compared to existing Weibull-based models. The innovation of this study is highlighted in two main areas. Firstly, it advances the theoretical development of the MIWD by conducting a thorough empirical assessment using actual customer transaction data instead of relying solely on simulated datasets. Secondly, it convincingly demonstrates the MIWD's superiority over conventional Weibull, inverse Weibull, and related sub-models through likelihood-based goodness-of-fit measures and functional analysis. Model parameters are estimated using the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) method, and the probability density, cumulative distribution, hazard, and survival functions are derived and analyzed to showcase the model's enhanced flexibility. By addressing the structural limitations of existing Weibull-type models and validating performance using real transaction data⁽¹⁰⁾, this study establishes the MIWD as a robust and superior option for lifetime analysis, customer transaction modeling, and reliability assessment.

2 Methodology

2.1 Modified Inverse Weibull Distribution (MIWD)

The four parameters of the $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \eta, t)$ probability distribution are α , β , γ , and η . The failure probability density function (PDF), which can be represented by it, is provided by:

$$f_{MIWD}(t) = \left(\alpha + \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t-\eta} \right)^{\beta-1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{t-\eta} \right)^2 \exp \left(-\frac{\alpha}{t-\eta} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t-\eta} \right)^\beta \right), \alpha > 0, \beta > 0, \gamma > 0, \eta < t < \infty$$

and the Modified Inverse Weibull probability distribution's many patterns are represented by the shape parameter β . In this case, γ is a location parameter that is also known as a guarantee time, failure-free period, or minimum life. It is a scale parameter that represents the typical life and is also positive. The Modified Inverse Weibull PDF's varied shape with $\beta (= 0.5, 1, 2, 2.5, 3)$, for $\alpha = 1, \gamma = 2$, and $\eta = 0$. It's crucial to remember that every number t is predicated on the idea that $\eta = 0$. $F_{MIWD}(t)$ (t) Represents the Modified

Inverse Weibull distribution's cumulative distribution function (or CDF), which is defined as

$$F_{MIW}(t) = \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t-\eta} - \gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^\beta\right)$$

There is no failure component by η when the Modified Inverse Weibull distribution's CDF is zero. η is referred to as the minimum life in the Modified Inverse Weibull CDF. When $t = \eta + \gamma$, the characteristic life is represented by $F_{MIW}(\eta + \gamma) = e^{-\frac{\alpha}{\gamma} - \gamma^{1-\beta}}$ for $\alpha = 1$ and $\gamma = 2$. The Modified Inverse Weibull CDF⁽¹¹⁾ particular instance with $\eta = 0$ and for values of $\gamma=2$ and $\beta(0.5, 1, 2, 2.5, 3)$

2.2 Reliability Analysis

For the examination of life time data, the Modified Inverse Weibull distribution can be a helpful description. $R_{MIW}(t)$ Also referred to as the survivor function, is the reliability function (RF) of the Modified Inverse Weibull distribution and is defined as $1 - F_{MIW}(t)$.

A feature of reliability analysis is the hazard rate function, which is defined by

$$R_{MIW}(t) = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t-\eta} - \gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^\beta\right)$$

A feature of reliability analysis is the hazard rate function, which is defined by

$$h_{MIW}(t) = \frac{f_{MIW}(t)}{1 - F_{MIW}(t)}$$

$$h_{MIW}(t) = \frac{\left(\alpha + \beta\gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^{\beta-1}\right)\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^2 \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t-\eta} - \gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^\beta\right)}{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t-\eta} - \gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^\beta\right)}$$

It is crucial to remember that the likelihood of failure per unit of time, distance, or cycles is represented by the units for $h_{MIW}(t)$.

Theorem 2.2.1 The hazard rate function of a Modified Inverse Weibull distribution has the following properties:

1. If $\beta = 2$, the failure rate is same as the $MIRD(\alpha, \gamma, \eta, t)$
2. If $\beta = 1$, the failure rate is same as the $MIED(\alpha, \gamma, \eta, t)$
3. If $\alpha = 0$, the failure rate is same as the $IWD(\beta, \gamma, \eta, t)$.

Proof. (a) Suppose $\beta = 2$, the failure rate is same as the $MIRD(\alpha, \gamma, \eta, t)$

$$h_{MIR}(t) = \frac{\left(\alpha + 2\gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)\right)\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^2 \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t-\eta} - \gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^2\right)}{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t-\eta} - \gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^2\right)}$$

(b) Suppose $\beta = 1$, the failure rate is same as the $MIED(\alpha, \gamma, \eta, t)$

$$h_{MIE}(t) = \frac{(\alpha + \gamma)\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^2 \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t-\eta} - \gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)\right)}{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t-\eta} - \gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)\right)}$$

(c) Suppose $\alpha = 0$, the failure rate is same as the $IWD(\beta, \gamma, \eta, t)$

$$h_{IW}(t) = \frac{\beta\gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^{\beta+1} \exp\left(-\gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^\beta\right)}{1 - \exp\left(-\gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^\beta\right)}$$

$H_{MIW}(t)$ Represents the Modified Inverse Weibull distribution's Cumulative Hazard Function (CHF), which is defined as

$$H_{MIW}(t) = -\ln\left|\exp\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t-\eta} - \gamma\left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^\beta\right)\right|$$

2.3 Statistical properties

The statistical characteristics of the $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \eta, t)$ are explained in this section.

2.3.1. Quantile and median

The actual solution to the following equation is the quantile t_q of the $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, t)$.

$$\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t_q}\right)^\beta + \frac{\alpha}{t_q} + \ln|1 - q| = 0$$

Since there isn't a closed form solution for the aforementioned equation in t_q , we can create alternative scenarios by changing the parametric variables in the quantile equation. Thus, the special situations that are deduced are

1. The q -the quantile of the $MIRD(\alpha, \gamma, t)$ by substituting $\beta = 2$

$$t_q = \frac{2\gamma}{-\alpha + \sqrt{\alpha^2 - 4\gamma \ln|1 - q|}}$$

2. The q -the quantile of the $IWD(\beta, \gamma, t)$ by substituting $\alpha = 0$

$$t_q = \left(\frac{-\gamma}{\ln|1 - q|}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}}$$

3. The q -the quantile of the $IRD(\gamma, t)$ by substituting $\alpha = 0, \beta = 2$

$$t_q = \sqrt{\frac{-\gamma}{\ln|1 - q|}}$$

4. The q -the quantile of the $IED(\gamma, t)$ by substituting $\alpha = 0, \beta = 1$

$$t_q = \frac{-\alpha}{\ln|1 - q|}$$

or by substituting $\beta = 1$

$$t_q = \frac{-(\alpha + \gamma)}{\ln|1 - q|}$$

By putting $q = 0.5$, we can get the median of $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \eta, t)$

2.3.2. Mode

The following non-linear equation with respect to t can be solved to yield the mode of the $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \eta, t)$.

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{t^2} + \beta\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta+1}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2\alpha}{t^3} + \beta(\beta+1)\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta+2}\right) = 0$$

There isn't a clear solution to the equation in its general form. The following special examples exist in the generic form:

- (1) If we put $\beta = 2$ and $\alpha = 0$,

$$\left(2\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^3\right)^2 - 6\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^4 = 0$$

Solving this equation in t , we get the mode as $Mod(t) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}\gamma}$

(2) If we put $\beta = 1$, then

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{t^2} + \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^2\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2\alpha}{t^3} + 2\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^3\right) = 0$$

Solving this equation in t , we get the mode as $Mod(t) = \frac{\alpha + \gamma}{2}$

(3) If we put $\alpha = 0$ then we have $IWD(\beta, \gamma, t)$ case, in this case the equation takes the following form

$$\left(\beta\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta+1}\right)^2 - \beta(\beta+1)\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta+2} = 0$$

Solving this equation in t , we get the mode as $Mod(t) = \left(\frac{\beta+1}{\beta\gamma}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}}$

2.3.3. Moments of $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, t)$ distributions

The following theorem gives the r^{th} moment of $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, t)$ distributions

Theorem 2.3.3.1: If T has the $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, t)$, the r^{th} moment of T , say μ_r , is given as follows

$$\mu_r = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \gamma^i}{i!} [\alpha^{r-i} \beta \Gamma(i\beta - r + 1) + \beta\gamma \alpha^{r-\beta(i+1)} \Gamma(\beta(i+1) - r)], & \text{for } \alpha, \beta, \gamma > 0 \\ \gamma^{\frac{r}{\beta}} \Gamma\left(1 - \frac{r}{\beta}\right), & \text{for } \alpha = 0, \beta, \gamma > 0 \\ \alpha^r \Gamma(1 - r), & \text{for } \alpha > 0, \beta, \gamma = 0 \end{cases}$$

Proof:

$$\mu_r = \int_{\eta}^{\infty} t^r f(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \eta, t) dt$$

$$\mu_r = \int_{\eta}^{\infty} t^r \left(\alpha + \beta\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^{\beta-1}\right) \left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^2 \text{Exp}\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t-\eta} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t-\eta}\right)^{\beta}\right) dt$$

Case A: In this case $\alpha > 0, \beta > 0, \gamma > 0$ and $\eta = 0$.

The exponent quantity $\text{Exp}\left(-\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta}\right)$

$$\text{Exp}\left(-\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta}\right) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \gamma^i \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{i\beta}}{i!}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_r &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \gamma^i}{i!} \int_0^{\infty} t^r \left(\alpha + \beta\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta-1}\right) \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{i\beta+2} \text{Exp}\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t}\right) dt \mu_r \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \gamma^i}{i!} \left(\int_0^{\infty} \alpha \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{-t+i\beta+2} \text{Exp}\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t}\right) dt + \int_0^{\infty} \beta\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{-t+i\beta+\beta+1} \text{Exp}\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t}\right) dt\right) \mu_r \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \gamma^i}{i!} [\alpha^{r-i} \beta \Gamma(i\beta - r + 1) + \beta\gamma \alpha^{r-\beta(i+1)} \Gamma(\beta(i+1) - r)] \end{aligned}$$

Case B: In the second case we assume that $\alpha = 0, \beta > 0, \gamma > 0$ and $\eta = 0$,

$$\mu_r = \int_0^{\infty} \beta\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{-r+\beta+1} \text{Exp}\left(-\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta}\right) dt$$

By substituting $w = \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^\beta$ then we get

$$\mu_r = \gamma^{\frac{r}{\beta}} \Gamma\left(1 - \frac{r}{\beta}\right) = \gamma^{\frac{r}{\beta}} \xi_r \xi_r = \Gamma\left(1 - \frac{r}{\beta}\right), r = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

Case C: In the third case we assume that $\alpha > 0, \beta = 0$ and $\eta = 0$

$$\mu_r = \int_0^\infty \alpha t^{r-2} \text{Exp}\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t}\right) dt$$

By substituting $w = \left(\frac{\alpha}{t}\right)$ then we get

$$\mu_r = \alpha^r \Gamma(1-r) = \alpha^r \omega_r \omega_r = \Gamma(1-r), r = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

$$CV_{MIW} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1} - 1} CS_{MIW} = \frac{\mu_3 - 3\mu_2\mu_1 + 2\mu_1^3}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} CK_{MIW} = \frac{\mu_4 - 4\mu_3\mu_1 + 6\mu_2\mu_1^2 - 3\mu_1^4}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1^2)^2}$$

2.4 Moment Generating Function

The moment generating function (MGF) of $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, t)$ is provided by the following theorem.

Theorem 2.4.1: If T has the $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, t)$, the moment generating function (mgf) of T , say $M(t)$ is given as follows

$$M(t) = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^i \gamma^i}{i!} \left[\frac{\alpha \Gamma(i\beta+1)}{(\alpha-t)^{i\beta+1}} + \frac{\beta \gamma \Gamma(\beta(i+1))}{(\alpha-t)^{\beta(i+1)}} \right] & \text{for } \alpha, \beta, \gamma > 0 \\ \sum_{i=0}^\infty \Gamma\left(1 - \frac{i}{\beta}\right) & \text{for } \alpha = 0, \beta, \gamma > 0 \\ \frac{\alpha}{\alpha-t} & \text{for } \alpha > 0, \beta, \gamma = 0 \end{cases}$$

Proof:

$$M(t) = \int_\eta^\infty e^{tx} f(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \eta, x) dx$$

$$M_{x^{-1}}(t) = \int_\eta^\infty \left(\alpha + \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{x-\eta}\right)^{\beta-1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{x-\eta}\right)^2 \text{Exp}\left(\frac{t}{x} - \frac{\alpha}{x-\eta} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{x-\eta}\right)^\beta\right) dx$$

By assuming that there is no minimum life

$$M_{x^{-1}}(t) = \int_0^\infty \left(\alpha + \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^{\beta-1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^2 \text{Exp}\left(\frac{t}{x} - \frac{\alpha}{x} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^\beta\right) dx$$

In example A, $\alpha > 0, \beta > 0, \gamma > 0$, and $\eta = 0$ are present.

$$M_{X^{-1}}(t) = \sum_{i=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^i \gamma^i}{i!} \int_0^\infty \left(\alpha + \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^{\beta-1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^{i\beta+2} \text{Exp}\left(\frac{t}{x} - \frac{\alpha}{x}\right) dx$$

$$M_{X^{-1}}(t) = \sum_{i=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^i \gamma^i}{i!} \left[\frac{\alpha \Gamma(i\beta+1)}{(\alpha-t)^{i\beta+1}} + \frac{\beta \gamma \Gamma(\beta(i+1))}{(\alpha-t)^{\beta(i+1)}} \right]$$

$$M_X(t) = \int_0^\infty \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^{\beta+1} \left(tx - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^\beta\right) dx$$

$$M_X(t) = \sum_{i=0}^\infty \frac{t^i \gamma^{\frac{i}{\beta}}}{i!} \Gamma\left(1 - \frac{i}{\beta}\right)$$

2.5 Least square estimation

Case A: Assume that $T_{(i)}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ represents the ordered sample, and let T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n be a random sample of the Modified Inverse Weibull distribution with cdf $F_{MIW}(t)$ With a sample size of n, we have

$$E(F(T_{(i)})) = \frac{i}{n+1}$$

$$Q(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(F(T_{(i)}) - \frac{i}{n+1} \right)^2$$

$$Q(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\text{Exp} \left(-\frac{\alpha}{t} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^\beta \right) - \frac{i}{n+1} \right)^2$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{t} \left(\text{Exp} \left(-\frac{\alpha}{t} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^\beta \right) - \frac{i}{n+1} \right) \text{Exp} \left(-\frac{\alpha}{t} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^\beta \right) = 0$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \text{Exp} \left(-\frac{\alpha}{t} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^\beta \right) = 0$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^\gamma \left(\text{Exp} \left(-\frac{\alpha}{t} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^\beta \right) - \frac{i}{n+1} \right) \beta \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^\gamma \ln \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)$$

$$\left(\text{Exp} \left(-\frac{\alpha}{t} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^\beta \right) - \frac{i}{n+1} \right) \text{Exp} \left(-\frac{\alpha}{t} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^\beta \right) = 0$$

$$Q(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(y_i - \frac{\alpha}{t} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^\beta \right)^2$$

The following equations result from differentiating based on these parameters:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n y \frac{1}{t} - \alpha \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{t^2} - \gamma \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{1+\beta} = 0$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n y \left(\frac{1}{t_i} \right)^\beta - \alpha \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{1+\beta} - \gamma \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{2\beta} = 0$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n y \left(\frac{1}{t_i} \right)^\beta \ln \left(\frac{1}{t_i} \right) - \alpha \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{1+\beta} \ln \left(\frac{1}{t_i} \right) - \gamma \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{2\beta} \ln \left(\frac{1}{t_i} \right) = 0$$

$$\hat{\gamma}_R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n y \left(\frac{1}{t_i} \right)^\beta \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^2 - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right) y \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{1+\beta}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{2\beta} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{t^2} - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{1+\beta} \right)^2}$$

$$\hat{\alpha}_R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n y \left(\frac{1}{t_i} \right)^\beta \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{1+\beta} - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right) y \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{2\beta}}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{1+\beta} \right)^2 - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t} \right)^{2\beta} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{t^2}}$$

Case C: Assume that $T_{(i)}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ represents the ordered sample, and let T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n be a random sample of $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, t)$ with cdf $F_{MIW}(t)$, With a sample size of n, we have

$$E(F(T_{(i)})) = \frac{i-0.3}{n+0.4}, T_1 < T_2 < \dots < T_n$$

$$\ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right) = \ln\gamma + \beta \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)$$

$$\text{Let } y = \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right), a = \ln\gamma, b = \beta, x = \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)$$

$$\hat{a} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right) \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^2 - \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right) \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right) \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right)}{n \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)\right)^2}$$

$$\hat{b} = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right) \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right) - \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right) \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)}{n \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)\right)^2}$$

The correlation coefficient of $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, t)$ by taking above assumptions

$$cc = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right) \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right) - \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right) \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)}{\sqrt{\left(n \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right)\right)^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right)\right)^2 \left(n \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)\right)^2\right)}}$$

The MIWD standard error of estimation $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, t)$ under the aforementioned assumptions

$$S_{y.x} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right)^2 - \ln\gamma \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right) - \beta \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right) \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right)}{n - k}}$$

Using the aforementioned assumptions, the MIWD coefficient of determination $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, t)$

$$R_{y.x}^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right)^2 - \ln\gamma \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right) - \beta \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right) \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right)}{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right)^2 - \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{F_{MIW}(t)}\right)\right)\right)^2}$$

2.6 Maximum Likelihood Estimation of the MIWD

The three parameters of the modified Inverse Weibull distribution $MIWD(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, t)$ pdf as the probability density function, consider the random samples t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n which consist of n observations. likelihood function with $\eta=0$ is defined as

$$L(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n; \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \eta) = \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\alpha + \beta\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta-1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^2 \text{Exp}\left(-\frac{\alpha}{t} - \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^\beta\right)$$

$$\ln L(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n; \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \eta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left(\alpha + \beta\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta-1}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^2 - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\alpha}{t}\right) - \gamma \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^\beta$$

$$\frac{\partial \ln L}{\partial \alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\left(\alpha + \beta\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta-1}\right)} - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right) = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ln L}{\partial \beta} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta-1} (1 + \beta \ln\left(\frac{1}{t}\right))}{\left(\alpha + \beta\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\beta-1}\right)} - \gamma \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^\beta \ln\left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right) = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ln L}{\partial \gamma} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1}}{\left(\alpha + \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1}\right)} - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \ln L}{\partial \alpha^2} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{-1}{\left(\alpha + \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1}\right)^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \ln L}{\partial \beta^2} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1} (1 + \beta \ln\left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)) \left(\alpha + \beta \ln\left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1} (\gamma - 1)\right)}{\left(\alpha + \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1}\right)^2} - \gamma \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta} \ln^2\left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \ln L}{\partial \gamma^2} = - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta^2 \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{2(\beta-1)}}{\left(\alpha + \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1}\right)^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \ln L}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{-\gamma \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1} (\beta \ln\left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right) + 1)}{\left(\alpha + \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1}\right)^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \ln L}{\partial \alpha \partial \gamma} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{-\beta \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1}}{\left(\alpha + \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1}\right)^2} \frac{\partial^2 \ln L}{\partial \beta \partial \gamma}$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1} (\beta \ln\left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right) + 1) (1 - \beta \gamma)}{\left(\alpha + \beta \gamma \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta-1}\right)} - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)^{\beta} \ln\left(\frac{1}{t_i}\right)$$

By solving above equations these solutions will yield the ML estimators $\hat{\alpha}$, $\hat{\beta}$ and $\hat{\gamma}$.

2.7 Real time Data with Mathematical Approach

To demonstrate the advantages of the Modified Inverse Weibull Distribution (MIWD), a real dataset is analysed in this section. The Maximum Likelihood Estimates (MLEs) of the model parameters, along with their corresponding standard errors (presented in parentheses), are obtained. For the dataset, the estimated Probability Density Function (PDF) of the MIWD model is presented. In addition, the corresponding plots of the PDF, Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF), hazard rate function, and survival function, based on the MLEs, are illustrated in Figure 1.

Real-time customer transactions on Kaggle.com are displayed in the data that was extracted from the website. The data set is as follows: 35.47, 2552.72, 115.97, 11.31, 62.21, 99.14, 145.94, 161.39, 77.73, 142.85, 928.68, 387.78, 142.07, 107.44, 54.31, 79.57, 441.18, 475.82, 106.26, 1468.14, 40.08, 39.87, 151.73, 17.05, 108.3, 366.56, and 924.23.

3 Results and Discussion

In this study, we propose the Modified Inverse Weibull Distribution (MIWD) and investigate its theoretical properties. Several statistical characteristics of the distribution are derived, including the quantile function, median, mode, moments, moment generating function, and least squares estimation. The analytical expressions for the probability density function (PDF) and hazard rate function of the MIWD are also obtained. The MIWD model demonstrates flexible behaviour in modelling lifetime

Fig 1. (a) PDF of modified inverse Weibull distribution. (b) CDF of modified inverse Weibull distribution for customer amount transaction data.(c) Hazard rate function of modified inverse Weibull distribution. (d) Survival functions of modified inverse Weibull distribution for customer amount transaction data.

data, exhibiting increasing, decreasing, and constant failure rate patterns. To evaluate the performance of the proposed model, Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) is applied to a real dataset related to nicotine levels in cigarettes. The results indicate that the proposed MIWD model provides a better fit compared with the traditional Modified Inverse Weibull distribution and its primary sub-models. Furthermore, the findings suggest that the proposed model can serve as a useful alternative framework for broader statistical analysis. Using the Python programming environment, we also illustrate the behaviour of various reliability functions of the modified distribution by applying it to real-time client transaction data obtained from Kaggle.

4 Conclusion

In this research, the four-parameter Modified Inverse Weibull Distribution (MIWD) is extensively analysed with respect to its theoretical properties and practical applicability as a flexible reliability model. By appropriately adjusting its parameters, the MIWD generalizes several classical lifetime distributions, enabling it to capture complex behaviours such as increasing, decreasing, and non-monotonic hazard rate patterns commonly observed in real-world lifetime data. To evaluate its practical performance, the proposed model was applied to a dataset of customer transaction amounts. The results demonstrate that the MIWD provides a superior fit compared with competing models, as supported by various quantitative goodness-of-fit criteria. Graphical analyses further validate these findings, where the estimated Probability Density Function (PDF), Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF), and hazard rate functions closely follow the empirical data histogram. This indicates the model’s

ability to effectively represent the skewness and heavy-tailed characteristics of the transaction data. Overall, the enhanced parameterization of the MIWD enables it to model a wide range of hazard rate behaviours, including rising and falling failure rates, making it a powerful and versatile tool for analysing both lifetime data and financial transaction datasets. The results highlight the superiority of the MIWD in fitting complex datasets and suggest its potential for broader applications in reliability engineering and customer behaviour modelling.

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